

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16542099

Impact Of Principals' Financial Management Practices On Quality Service Delivery In Public Secondary School In Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of Principals' financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study, descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the comprised of 1,710 teachers drawn from 43 public secondary schools in Jalingo and Ardo-kola local government areas of Taraba State respectively, 313 teachers were randomly sampled. The research instrument was a questionnaire titled; "Financial Management and Quality Service Questionnaire" (FMQSQ). The FMQSQ was validated by three experts from the faculty of education. The reliability of FMQSQ was established using Cronbach-alpha method which yielded a reliability index of .79 index, the data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of while hi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study shows that Principals' financial management practices (Practices such as mobilization of fund, budgeting and monitoring of school fund) significantly impact on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria it was concluded that there is a strong and positive impact of financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary schools. Based on the findings it is therefore, recommended among others that Principals should be trained and empowered to mobilize school funds effectively from diverse sources, including internally generated revenue, government grants, and community partnerships, to enhance quality service delivery in their respective schools.

Keywords: Principals, Management, Financial Management, Principals' Financial Management Practices and Quality Service Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Quality service delivery is one of the key building blocks in any education system (Nyirenda, n.d.). Services should be delivered with certain quality, for learners to access and use to ultimately improve their knowledge and skills status. In education service, quality delivery is considered as a degree of

performance in relation to a defined standard of intervention known to be safe and have the capacity to improve education within available resources. Mtaho and Ishengoma, (2014), considered Quality of Service as the effect of system service performance that defines the level of a user's satisfaction with the service. In order to achieve the quality service delivery by a particular system, performance evaluation on a system should focus on specifying and solving the problems that occur. In addition to that, performance evaluation of an existing system focuses on how the system is doing the right things and delivering good quality of service. Quality is one thing that customers look for in an offer. It is related to the value of an offer, which could suggest satisfaction or dissatisfaction on the part of the users or customers (Timothy & Michael, 2023). The service in school setting is a process involving a series of intangible activities which in most cases, take place as an interaction between the students and teachers or physical resources or systems of the service provider - which are provided as solutions to the students' problems.

Service delivery in other hand, refers to the actual accomplishment of assigned task related to the administration and management of educational services in public secondary schools. These tasks include ensuring effective teaching and learning, maintaining infrastructure, providing adequate instructional materials, fostering a conducive learning environment, and promoting student welfare. Amaewhule and Udofia (2022) noted that service delivery is the interaction among the students, the teacher, the content, the knowledge, skills, dispositions students will need for learning and collaborating with others. Service delivery as well as competencies is essential practices that, teachers must master for instructional delivery to maximize knowledge and skill acquisition. quality service delivery is a complex phenomenon especially in relation to the concept of management. Instructional delivery is the actual work done against the expected standard of achievement. There are numerous activities which teachers carry out that determine how effective and productive their job might be, such activities include the drawing or preparing of scheme of work, lesson plan, delivery of lesson, evaluation of students, reporting of student progress. Other activities carried out by teachers include, maintenance of discipline among students, keeping of attendance register, house mastership/mistress, counseling, participation in sports and club activities. These are areas which relate to the individual teacher's service delivery needs. Quality service delivery is also a presentation of information or skills clearly and enthusiastically, non-judgmental and relaxed, keeping the lessons task-oriented, aim at students' achievement and interact with students through probing questions and assist students by elaborating their answers (Cresswell, 2015). Quality service delivery in secondary school system depends largely on Principals' financial management practices to achieve its goals and objectives

The principal is the central nerve of school activities in secondary school education. He or she has to manage the school to bring about the achievement of its goals and objective. The principal therefore manages both human, material and financial resources to actualize the goal of education. Ayeni (2012), stressed that principalship is not just a name for chief executive position but a great responsibility to ensure general school administration in attaining instructional leadership through coordinating curricula and co-curricular programmes. Onuma (2016) also stated that the vitality of the school rests with the principal's functional leadership traits that is capable of invigorating and stimulating teachers or students to attain institutional aims and objectives. Onuma (2016) further reiterated that the primary function of principals in in secondary school education is to exhibit effective instructional leadership for the enhancement of varied curriculum as well as quality of instructional programme for attainment of educational goals. Monitoring in its ramifications is a cardinal role of a secondary school principal to ensure effectiveness in teaching and learning. Education Development Trust (2016) affirmed that effective head-teachers provide clear vision with a sense of direction for steering activities of a school. The Education Development Trust (2016) also mentioned that effective head teachers have the obligation of focusing more attention on staff based on what is imperative and will not let them get distracted with initiatives that will not have impact on students' academic attainment; head teachers know what is going on in their classrooms; he or she knows the financial needs of their school, they have a clear view of the strengths and weaknesses of their staff; they know how to build on the strengths and reduce the

weaknesses and on their staff programme and development on the real needs of their staff and school through effective management or administrative functions.

Management refers to the use of limited resources such as human, material and financial combined with forecasting, planning, leadership and execution skills to achieved predetermined specific goals. Sethy (2022) sees Management as a distinct process of planning, organizing, coordinating, actuating and controlling, performed to determine and accomplish stated objectives with the use of human beings and other resources. This means that Principals have the responsibility of forecasting, planning, organizing, to coordinate the teachers with the use of financial resources in order to achieve quality service delivery in school. This also means that management is the process of planning, setting of educational goals and policies, harnessing and managing resources systematically to comprehend predetermined goals. It also implies that the achievement of educational goals of any nation could be accomplished by friendly school effective management which includes planning, organizing, coordinating, staffing, budgeting, sourcing of fund, controlling, maintenance of school discipline among staff and students. In the other hand Okwori (2016) referred to financial management as the forecasting, planning, organizing, directing and controlling of all activities relating to the generation and application of financial resources of an enterprise in keeping with the financial objectives. The author proceeded that financial management is a series of managerial tasks which are directed to the provision, use and disbursement of the economic resources of an entity in ways consistent with the function of the entity. Okwori (2016) went further to explain that financial management is not some superior kind of accounting; that rather it brings into focus the strictly financial issues in the evaluation of all courses of action and the consequences.

The phrase "financial management practices" refers to the area of finance with a long-term objective that is consistent with the firm's or enterprise's strategic goals (Barney & Hesterly, 2015; Simon & Mohammed, 2017). The goal of financial management practices is to satisfy the organization's goals and objectives and also maximize shareholder wealth. In this study, mobilization, budgeting, monitoring, evaluation and auditing of school fund are the variables for Principals' financial management practice for quality service delivery in secondary schools.

Mobilization or generation of school fund is a financial management practice which refers to exploring other ways to source for finance and making better use of and maximizing new and existing financial resources (Elijah & Haldess, 2022) The use of financial mobilization practice is associated with better revenue collection and utilization. The principal is expected to source or generate funds for management of the school. Beyond sourcing for fund, the principal has the responsibility of managing the available cash in the school to avoid waste and displacement of priorities in attending to school needs. Principals of secondary schools in Jalingo education Zone depend on generated funds such as examination fees, and P.T.A levies, sales of school farm products, lunching and so on. Irrespective of all the sources of funds available to secondary school principals, some school activities and programmes are not being handled effectively because of inadequate funds. Insufficient funds may hinder the provision or procurement of infrastructural facilities, such as laboratory equipment, computers, power plants, audio-visual aids and stationeries among other facilities that enhances the operation of the school. Inadequate school facilities may also frustrate school programmes and ultimately aborts educational goals and objectives. It has been observed, that principals seemed to have less attitude on the mobilization of school fund towards the achievement of school goals, principals in the 21st century are expected to generate or mobilize fund for enhancement of quality service delivery in secondary school, apart from Government allocation. However, it has been observed that most of the principals have little or no knowledge or strategies for mobilizing or generating school fund to enhance quality service delivery, instead, over depending on Government allocation.

Budgeting in the other hand, refers to detailed plan, which sets out, in money terms, the plans for income and expenditure in respect of the future period of time. It is important for the principals to be prepared in advance of the time period and agreed on the objectives for that period of time together with the strategy planned to achieve those objectives (Rafael & David, 2017). Budgeting as a financial management practice is one of the most important tools of planning and control after fund generation or sourcing. The

principal stages of budgeting process include communicating the details of objectives and strategy to those responsible for the preparation of budgets, determining the limiting factor which restricts overall budget flexibility and forms the focus of the budget cascades, preparing initial budgets, negotiating budgets with line managers, coordinating and review budgets, accepting budgets in final form and finally carrying out an on-going review of budgets (Rafael & David, 2017). Budgets are financial blueprints that quantify a plan for a future period. Budgets require management to specify expected sales, cash inflows and outflows, and costs; and they provide a mechanism for effective planning and control in organizations in order to achieve quality service delivery. The budget is a standard against which the actual performance can be compared and measured. In Jalingo education Zone, quality service delivery among teachers and other staff seemed to be poor and inadequately carried out or executed. This situation is worrisome to stakeholders in the Zone. Stakeholders in education attributed poor and inadequate quality service delivery in secondary schools to poor and inadequate preparation or school budget by principals in advance to cater for the activities and programmes of secondary school, hence, poor and inadequate quality service delivery. Some stakeholders in Education in the Zone, attributed poor and inadequate quality service delivery to non-compliance of school budget on particular school programme and activities to enhance quality service delivery in the Zone. It is not uncommon that many school principals often not examine the financial statement of their schools, which has partly caused teachers' disenchantment in service delivery and resulted in low quality service delivery in public secondary schools. It is against this background that the researcher intends to carry out a study on impact of principals' financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria, with a view to improving quality service delivery in secondary schools.

Liu, (2019) carried out a study on the impact of Principal Leadership on School Funding and Student Achievement in public secondary schools in California, USA. The findings revealed that Principals' mobilization of funds positively impacts student achievement. Similarly, Hall et al. (2018) carried out a study on Mobilizing Resources for School Improvement: The Role of Principals in public secondary schools in Ontario, Canada the findings of the study revealed that principals' mobilization of funds enhances teacher morale and student learning outcomes. Additionally, Kim et al. (2020) investigated the Effect of Principal Fund Mobilization on School Quality in public secondary schools in Seoul, South Korea. The findings of the study revealed that principals' mobilization of funds improves school quality, including teacher quality and student achievement. Lee, (2017) investigated the principals' mobilization of fund as Financial Management and School Performance in public secondary schools in Texas Findings revealed that principals' financial management skills, including fund mobilization, positively impact school performance. In the same vein, Chukwuka et al (2019) investigated the impact of budget preparation and implementation on secondary schools in South East Nigeria. The study revealed that budget preparation procedure and implementation enhance secondary school administration, gender has no significant influence on the extent which principals' budget preparation procedure and implementation enhances secondary school administration. Notwithstanding Eze and Onyene (2020) carried out a study on budgeting practices and effective school administration in Anambra State, Nigeria. Finding of the study revealed that Principals' budgeting practices include stock taking, market survey, preparing budget singlehandedly, and adhering to fiscal calendar. Ironke (2024) also, investigated financial management practices and administrative effectiveness of secondary principals in Anambra State, Nigeria the findings revealed that there is relationship between principals' financial management (financial planning, financial budgeting and financial disbursement monitoring) and administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the problem

There has been a recurring public discussion on the issue of quality service delivery by school teachers particularly in secondary schools in Jalingo education Zone, Taraba State. The series of complaints has been from students, guardians, parents and other education stakeholders. The researcher also observed that the type of education provided by most public secondary schools does not meet the society's demand

in terms of quality service delivery as students' outcome does not match the government and parental investments. This seems to amount to high rate of mass failure of students in most of the National Examinations, inadequate skill acquisition and the culminated anti-social behaviours among secondary school leavers. Some stakeholders in education attributed these unpleasant experiences to poor quality service delivery by school administrators, and teachers. Some stakeholders in education in the Zone, also attributed poor quality service delivery in secondary to inability of secondary schools' principals to mobilize, and budget school fund as when due.

Despite the effort of the state government through the state ministry of education and teaching service board to ensure that every principal manages school finance so as to enhance quality service delivery yet the issues of poor quality of service delivery persisted. It is against this background that the researcher intends to carry out a study on impact of principals' financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria, with a view to improving quality service delivery in secondary school.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine impact of Principals' financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the impact of principals':

1. Mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary school in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. Budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of principals' budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study 1,710 teachers drawn from 43 public secondary schools in Jalingo and Ardo-kola local government areas respectively, 313 teachers were randomly sampled. The research instrument was a questionnaire titled; Financial Management and Quality Service Questionnaire" (FMQSQ). The FMQSQ was validated by three experts from the faculty of education. The reliability of FMQSQ was established using Cronbach-alpha method which yielded a reliability index of 0.89. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic of chi-square. The mean score of 2.50 scores was used as a criterion mean score for decision making on each item. The mean score of 2.50 and above was accepted and below 2.50 was rejected as not having desired impact; while the chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question one: *What is the impact of principals’ mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations Rating Scale on the Impact of principals’ mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria

Statement	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1. Principal's mobilization of funds for teacher training has improved the quality of teaching.	3.48	0.82	A
2. Principal's allocation of funds for library resources has enhanced student access to information for improved performance.	3.14	1.06	A
3. Principal's mobilization of funds for infrastructure development has improved the learning environment.	2.99	1.09	A
4. Principal's use of funds for student support services has promoted quality learning outcome.	3.19	1.03	A
5. Principal's mobilization of funds for technology integration has enhanced teaching/learning effectiveness.	3.10	1.02	A
6. Principal's allocation of school funds has supported extracurricular activities for quality service delivery.	3.31	0.90	A
7. Principal's allocation of funds for extracurricular activities has promoted teachers’ quality delivery.	3.24	1.00	A
8. Principal's use of funds for school maintenance has ensured a safe learning environment for quality delivery.	3.10	1.09	A
Cluster Mean/Standard deviation	3.19	1.01	HI

Source: Field work (2025). Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50 \Rightarrow$ Agreed; $X \leq 2.50 \Rightarrow$ Strongly disagreed

Results in table 1 show response on the Impact of principals’ mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. All the items have the mean rating scales in the region of 2.5 to 3.48 which shows that principals’ mobilization of school fund have impact on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.19; this implies that when principals mobilize school fund it enhances quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the Impact of principals’ budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviations Rating Scale on the Impact of principals’ budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Statement	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1. Principal's budget allocation for instructional materials adequately supports teaching needs in the school.	3.19	1.01	A
2. Principal's budgeting for professional development has enhanced my teaching skills.	3.36	0.86	A
3. Principal's budget allocation for classroom maintenance has ensures a conducive learning environment in the school.	3.11	1.01	A
4. Principal's budgeting for technology integration improves my teaching efficiency in the school.	3.22	0.97	A
5. Principal's budget allocation for student support services helps to improve my students’ performance.	3.03	1.03	A
6. Principal's budgeting for extracurricular activities enriches the school's learning environment.	3.05	0.95	A

7. Principal's budget allocation for teacher welfare improves job satisfaction for effective teaching/learning.	3.14	1.01	A
8. Principal's budgeting for school infrastructure improves the overall learning environment.	3.17	0.98	A
Cluster Mean/Standard deviation	3.16	0.98	A

Source: Field work (2025). Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50 \Rightarrow$ Agreed; $X \leq 2.50 \Rightarrow$ Strongly disagreed

Results in table 2 show responses on the Impact of principals' budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. All the items have the mean rating scales in the region of 2.5 to 3.36 which shows that the principals' budgeting of school fund significantly impact on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.16; this implies that respondents unanimously agreed on the principals' budgeting of school fund impact on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Null Hypothesis one

There is no significant impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-square Test on impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	82.899	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	76.203	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	70.717	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	313		

From Table 6, chi-square at 20 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 82.899, p = .000$). This signifies that there is significant impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria is not retained. Rejecting the hypothesis which implies that principals' mobilization of school fund enhances quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	83.699	20	.032
Likelihood Ratio	78.665	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	80.042	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	313		

Table 7 presents chi-square test at 20 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 83.699, p = .032$). This signifies that there is significant impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria is not retained. Rejecting the hypothesis implies that Principals' budgeting of school fund significantly impact on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that:

1. Principals' mobilization of school fund significantly impacts on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. Principals' budgeting of school fund significantly impacts on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer all the two research questions on the independent variable; however, the chi-square statistics was used for the analysis of the hypotheses on the impact of Principals' financial management practices on quality service delivery in public secondary school in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

The mean and standard deviation scores rating items on the impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.19; this implies that when principals mobilize school fund it enhances quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Similarly, chi-square at 20 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 82.899$, $p = .000$). Signifies that chi-square at 20 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 82.899$, $p = .000$). This signifies that there is significant impact of principals' mobilization of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

The result is in agreement with the result of Liu, (2019) carried out a study on the impact of Principal Leadership on School Funding and Student Achievement in public secondary schools in California, USA. The findings revealed that Principals' mobilization of funds positively impacts student achievement. The present study supports the findings of Hall et al. (2018) carried out a study on Mobilizing Resources for School Improvement: The Role of Principals in public secondary schools in Ontario, Canada the findings of the study revealed that principals' mobilization of funds enhances teacher morale and student learning outcomes. The findings of the study support that of Kim et al. (2020) investigated the Effect of Principal Fund Mobilization on School Quality in public secondary schools in Seoul, South Korea. The findings of the study revealed that principals' mobilization of funds improves school quality, including teacher quality and student achievement. Nevertheless, the findings are in agreement with the work of Lee, (2017) who investigated the principals' mobilization of fund as Financial Management and School Performance in public secondary schools in Texas Findings revealed that principals' financial management skills, including fund mobilization, positively impact school performance.

The mean and standard deviation scores rating items on the Impact of principals' budgeting of school fund on quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.16; this implies that respondents unanimously agreed on the principals' budgeting of school fund can influence quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. Also, hypothesis tested with chi-square test at 20 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 83.699$, $p = .032$). signifies that there is significant impact of principals' budgeting of school fund and quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

The study is in agreement with the study conducted by Chukwuka et al (2019) investigated the impact of budget preparation and implementation on secondary schools in South East Nigeria. The study revealed that budget preparation procedure and implementation enhance secondary school administration, gender has no significant influence on the extent which principals' budget preparation procedure and implementation enhances secondary school administration. Notwithstanding the finding of this study is not contrary to the findings of Eze and Onyene (2020) carried out a study on budgeting practices and effective school administration in Anambra State, Nigeria. Finding of the study revealed that Principals' budgeting practices include stock taking, market survey, preparing budget singlehandedly, and adhering to

fiscal calendar. The findings are in agreement with the work of Ironke, (2024) investigated financial management practices and administrative effectiveness of secondary principals in Anambra State, Nigeria the findings revealed that there is relationship between principals' financial management (financial planning, financial budgeting and financial disbursement monitoring) and administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

Base on the findings of this study, it is concluded that there is a strong and positive impact of financial management practices on the quality service delivery in public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should be trained and empowered to mobilize school funds effectively from diverse sources, including internally generated revenue, government grants, and community partnerships, to enhance quality service delivery.
2. Regular training should be provided to principals on strategic budgeting and transparent allocation of school funds, ensuring alignment with priority educational needs.

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